

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF THE FISH PRODUCTION MARKET OF THE KYRGYZ REPUBLIC

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Abstract

Analysis of the current state of the fish production market in the Kyrgyz Republic allows us to identify trends, challenges and prospects for this industry in modern conditions. The article is aimed at providing a comprehensive overview of fish production in this region, identifying key factors influencing the quality and safety of fish production and its processing products

Keywords: fish production, aquaculture.

Purpose of the study: *Analysis of the current state of the fish production market in the Kyrgyz Republic to identify trends, challenges and prospects for this industry in modern conditions.*

Materials and methods.

To analyze the current state of the fish production market in the Kyrgyz Republic, we used: Statistical data from national statistical agencies and ministries, documents and reports (reports and publications of international organizations (FAO) on the state of the fishing industry

National strategies and programs for the development of fisheries, economic reviews and forecasts, literary sources (scientific articles and studies on the topic of fish production, books and monographs on fisheries, information from the media and industry publications (articles in newspapers, magazines and online portals about the state of and market trends).

Secondary data analysis (collection and analysis of existing statistics, reports and publications, use of data to determine current trends and market dynamics, SWOT analysis (identification of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats for the fish production market), supply chain analysis (research of all stages supply chain, from production to the final consumer, identifying bottlenecks and problem areas).

Introduction.

The Kyrgyz Republic, having significant water resources, has the potential to develop the fisheries sector, but this sector is at the beginning of its development.

In this article we will analyze current trends, problems, and also consider possibilities for its further development.

Adequate nutrition is the basis of healthy human nutrition, being one of the most important aspects of the prevention of nutrition-related diseases, it determines the need for fish nutrition in the diet of the population to maintain the functioning of the most important human organs.

Fish farming is a branch of agriculture that is engaged in the cultivation of fish, crayfish and shellfish in artificial waters or special farms. The purpose of fish farming is to obtain products, such as fresh or frozen fish and caviar, and to create conditions for its growth. [1].

Fish and seafood consumption is an important part of human nutrition and health. Fish and seafood are an important element in the diet, providing the human body with the necessary nutrients.

This is an important branch of agriculture in many countries with direct access to the sea and ocean, and is an essential part of providing the population with healthy and nutritious products necessary for rational nutrition and maintaining human health.

The nutritional value of fish is varied and healthy and contains components such as proteins, fats, carbohydrates, vitamins, minerals and other biologically active substances. The protein contained in fish is high quality and complete, containing all the necessary amino acids, including lysine and leucine, essential fatty acids, including unique eicosapentaenoic and docosahexaenoic acids in ratios favorable for the human body.

Fish oil is rich in polyunsaturated fatty acids, including omega-3 and omega-6, which have positive effects on cardiovascular health and brain function.

Fat is also an important source of energy and minerals, B vitamins, including B12, vitamin D, A, E, necessary for maintaining health. They are needed in order

to maintain healthy skin, vision, immunity, and body functioning.

Proteins in fish are an important source of high-quality, complete protein. Contains all the necessary amino acids for health and growth, an important source of high-quality complete protein, contains all the necessary vitamins, including lysine, leucine and essential fatty acids, such as unique eicosapentaenoic and docosahexaenoic acids, which are beneficial to the human body.

Fish muscles contain little coarse connective tissue, which makes them tender and juicy. They play a key role in tissue growth and repair, as well as providing the body with energy. Fish contains various minerals and vitamins, which are an important source of energy, minerals and fat-soluble vitamins. Minerals such as iron, zinc, calcium, phosphorus, magnesium and potassium, which are essential for maintaining healthy bones, muscles, blood and other body systems.

In addition, fish is a source of B vitamins, vitamin D, vitamin A and vitamin E, which are essential for maintaining healthy skin, vision and the immune system.

Fish contains various bioactive substances such as antioxidants, polyphenols, pigments and other compounds that may have beneficial effects on health.

Thus, fish is often an alternative to meat in the diet, especially for people following a healthy lifestyle or following fat-restricted diets. Thanks to its high protein and polyunsaturated fatty acid content, fish is an attractive choice for those seeking a balanced diet. The ease of preparing fish dishes is explained by its popularity in cooking and is distinguished by a variety of cooking methods, which makes it a convenient and popular choice for daily meals. In terms of speed of digestibility, fish and dairy products are identical and occupy first place [1]

Results and discussion.

The average per capita consumption of fish and fish products in the Kyrgyz Republic does not significantly reach the established norm. This highlights the need to increase nutrition awareness among the population and the importance of including fish in the diet to maintain health. According to the average physiological standards established in the country, each person should consume 9.1 kg of fish products per year. However, according to the latest data, in 2018, the average per capita consumption of fish and fish products in the Kyrgyz Republic was only 1.9 kg per person per year, which is 4.7 times less than the established norm. [3]

The Kyrgyz Republic, one of the five Central Asian republics, located in the center of the Eurasian space, is characterized by the lack of access to the ocean. This geographical location has a significant im-

act on fisheries and fish production in the region. Water resources are an important component of the natural wealth of the Kyrgyz Republic, and the development of fisheries and aquaculture plays a significant role in ensuring food security, socio-economic development of the country, including the income of the population.

According to the Law of the Kyrgyz Republic dated March 17, 2021 No. 35 "On aquaculture, fishing and protection of aquatic biological resources", all public water bodies are water bodies of state importance. Fishery reservoirs of national importance include lakes Issyk-Kul, Son-Kul and Toktogul, Bazar-Korgon, Kirov, and Orto-Tokoy reservoirs. Lake Issyk-Kul is a fishery reservoir of national importance with the zoning of the biosphere territory "Issyk-Kol" into separate zones (main zone, buffer zone, transition zone, remediation zone) with a special regime of protection and use. [4]

The total area of lakes, reservoirs, ponds and other bodies of water suitable for fisheries and aquaculture is more than 701,100 hectares. These reservoirs are home to more than 70 species of fish, although only a limited number of species are of commercial value. The largest number of fish species live in lakes and reservoirs of Kyrgyzstan, especially in Lake Issyk-Kul. After the introduction of a ban on fishing in lakes Issyk-Kul and Son-Kul, commercial fishing is mainly carried out in large fishery reservoirs, such as the Toktogul reservoir, Kirov, Orto-Tokoy and Bazar-Korgon reservoirs. The main species subject to commercial fishing include Issyk-Kul trout, whitefish, peled, common carp, bream, tench, pike perch, grass carp, silver carp and marinka. Today, there are hundreds of private enterprises involved in pond fish farming. In addition to them, the state enterprise "Uzgen Fishery" is engaged in the production of marketable fish in ponds. [3]

Despite this, measures are being taken to release juvenile salmon, whitefish and carp fish into various water bodies of the country, which contributes to the development of fish farming and aquaculture. But at the same time, experience shows that fish farming is possible in this region, and modern fish farming technologies in RCW (recirculating water supply system), cages and others are very widely used. The region has a wide variety of water resources, here you can find mountain rivers and reservoirs with both fresh and salt water, a large irrigation network, lakes with fresh and salt water, several large rivers and the opportunity to engage in fish farming in the lakes of the republic. All this makes the region so different from others and creates conditions for the development of various areas of fish farming. [4]

The dynamics of commercial fish production in the Kyrgyz Republic over recent years of development can be seen in Table 1

Table 1

Years	2013 год	2014 год	2015 год	2016 год	2017 год	2018 год
Fish catch, tons	654,0	805,3	1100,3	2020	2138,4	2577,0

(*) data from the Department of Pastures, Livestock and Fisheries of the Ministry of Agriculture. [3]

The following areas of fisheries are being developed in the Kyrgyz Republic: pond fish farming, fishing and fish processing, cage fish farming. Pond fish

farming is a direction in which artificial fertilization and incubation of eggs occurs, obtaining larvae and

raising them. One of the main directions for the development of fisheries in Kyrgyzstan. Technologies such as closed water supply systems (CRWS) are actively used in this direction. Pond fish farming is the most rational and cost-effective way to grow fish. the main and most productive direction of modern aquaculture in the Kyrgyz Republic. A significant barrier to the growth of commercial fish production is the absence in the republic of specialized enterprises for the production of complete fish feed that are economically accessible to fishery entities. In the Kyrgyz Republic, pond fish farming is carried out, where artificial fertilization and incubation of eggs is carried out, as well as the rearing of larvae and fish. Pond fish farming stands out as the main and most productive area of aquaculture in the country, given the total area of lakes and reservoirs, as well as the presence of a large number of rivers fed by springs and melting glaciers.

Fishing and fish processing: The most developed in this direction are Lake Issyk-Kul and the adjacent territories. This area includes both catching fish and its subsequent processing. The most important problems in this fisheries sector are the lack of incentives for investment in high-performance fishing equipment and logistics, as well as poaching, which depletes fish resources.

In the Republic, commercial fishing, after the ban (Law of the Kyrgyz Republic “On the prohibition of production, transportation, acquisition, sale and export of especially valuable and endemic melting fish in lakes Issyk-Kul and Son-Kul” dated August 4, 2008 No. 191 (as amended by the Law KR dated March 3, 2009 No. 73) for fishing in lakes Issyk-Kul and SonKul, was carried out mainly in large fishery reservoirs developed by fisheries: the Toktogul, Kirov, Orto-Tokoy and Bazar-Korgon reservoirs.

The main commercial fish species in reservoirs and lakes are Issyk-Kul trout, whitefish, peled, common carp, bream, tench, pike perch, grass carp, silver carp, and marinka. The reservoirs of the Issyk-Kul region are home to 35-37 species of fish. The only commercial fish of Lake Issyk-Kul are: carp, carp, marinka, osman, bream, trout, whitefish, pike perch, chebak and chebak (out of 28 species registered to date).

Before the ban on fishing was introduced, about 30 fishing entities were engaged in commercial fishing. The most important problems in this fisheries sector are the lack of incentives for investment in high-performance fishing equipment and logistics, as well as poaching, which depletes fish resources. To date, commercial fishing is not carried out in large fishery reservoirs. The Department of Fisheries under the Ministry of Agriculture of the Kyrgyz Republic carries out activities for the release (stocking) of juvenile salmon, whitefish and carp fish species into lakes Issyk-Kul, Son-Kul, Orto-Tokoy Reservoir and other reservoirs of the Kyrgyz Republic.[5]

On March 28, 2023. 100 thousand juvenile Issyk-Kul trout weighing 185 mg were released into 13 fishing grounds (Ton River); 50 thousand juvenile trout were released into the Ak-Terek area (fishing area 9). 40 thousand juvenile Issyk-Kul trout were stocked into the Tyup River [6]

Cage fish farming is a young trend that began to actively develop in 1989. Cage fish farming involves the cultivation of rainbow trout in cages, which represents a promising sector of fisheries. Existing trout processing farms in the Kyrgyz Republic have the potential to reach a volume of about 5 thousand tons per year, which opens up prospects for the development of production and export of fish products.[6]

Growing fish in cages is possible in almost the entire vast water area of the Naryn reservoir cascade. The basin method of growing commercial fish also has great potential, which can be developed throughout the republic, but this area requires large investments. A significant barrier to the growth of commercial fish production is the absence in the republic of specialized enterprises for the production of complete fish feed that are economically accessible to fishery entities.

The development of aquaculture is also hampered by low fish processing capacity and unresolved logistics problems for the rapid delivery of high-quality fresh and live fish products to large populated areas. The potential of existing trout processing farms in the Kyrgyz Republic is about 5 thousand tons per year. [6]

The Kyrgyz Republic actively interacts with the states of Central Asia and the Eurasian Economic Union within the framework of agreed agro-industrial policies. Participation in the Central Asia and Caucasus Fisheries and Aquaculture Commission opens up new opportunities for the exchange of experience and information, as well as for joint research and projects in the field of fisheries and aquaculture.

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The FAO Council at its Hundred and Thirty-seventh Session on October 1, 2009 adopted the “Agreement on the Establishment of the Fisheries and Aquaculture Commission in Central Asia and the Caucasus”, of which the Kyrgyz Republic is also a member of the Commission.[6]

Since August 12, 2015, according to the Treaty on Accession to the Countries of the Eurasian Economic Union, the Kyrgyz Republic has become the fifth member of the Eurasian Economic Union (hereinafter referred to as the Union, EAEU), for which one of the promising areas is cooperation in the field of aquaculture. [7].

Activities in the field of aquaculture of the Kyrgyz Republic and the safety of fish and fish products are mainly regulated by the following regulatory and legislative

acts:

- Law of the Kyrgyz Republic dated March 17, 2021 No. 35 “On aquaculture, fisheries and protection of aquatic biological resources”]; [8].

- Government Decree No. 546 dated October 15, 2019 “Program for the development of fisheries and aquaculture in the Kyrgyz Republic for 2019-2023” (No. 546 dated October 15, 2019);

- Technical Regulations of the EAEU “On the Safety of Fish and Fish Products” (EAEU TR 040/2016), which was adopted by Decision of the Council of the Eurasian Economic Commission No. 162 of October 18, 2016 and came into force on September 1, 2017; [9].

Fisheries and aquaculture have great potential for development in the Kyrgyz Republic, especially in the context of growing demand for fish products and increasing exports. To achieve this goal, measures must be taken to stimulate investment, combat poaching and improve infrastructure in the fisheries and aquaculture sector. Through joint efforts of the government, international organizations and the private sector, significant results can be achieved in this area.

The SWOT analysis (analysis of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats) for fish production in the Kyrgyz Republic based on the above is as follows:

Strengths:

1. Unique natural conditions: The geographical location of the country and the diversity of water resources create unique opportunities for the development of fish farming.

2. Legislative support: The legislation of Kyrgyzstan on aquaculture and fisheries provides state protection of water resources and stimulates the development of this industry.

3. Diversity of fish species: More than 70 species of fish live in the water bodies of Kyrgyzstan, which provides a wide range of opportunities for the development of industrial and pond fish farming.

4. Use of modern technologies: The use of modern fish farming technologies, including recirculating water supply systems (RAS), helps to increase the productivity and efficiency of the industry.

Weak sides:

1. Lack of investment: Lack of incentives to invest in modern fishing equipment and logistics hampers the development of the industry and reduces its competitiveness.

2. Poaching: The problem of poaching is a serious threat to the sustainable use of fisheries resources, which can lead to depletion of stocks and loss of biodiversity.

Possibilities:

1. Adopt modern practices: There is potential for the introduction of modern fish farming methods and technologies, which can improve the productivity and competitiveness of the industry.

2. Development of pond fish farming: The development of pond fish farming can become a promising direction for entrepreneurs and state enterprises, given the availability of reservoirs suitable for this purpose.

Threats:

1. Depletion of fish resources: Continued poaching and ineffective management of fish resources can lead to depletion of stocks and deterioration of the ecological situation in water bodies.

2. Impact of climate change: Changes in climate can affect the ecosystems of water bodies, which can negatively affect the breeding and cultivation of fish.

As a result of the SWOT analysis, key factors influencing fish production in the Kyrgyz Republic were identified and strategies for the development of the industry were determined, taking into account its strengths and weaknesses, as well as the opportunities and threats it faces.

Conclusions and offers :

Based on the results of the analysis of the state of the industry in the Kyrgyz Republic, the following priorities can be determined to ensure the effectiveness of the work being carried out in order to develop this industry:

- Increase cooperation between states and sectors involved in the management and protection of natural resources regarding the control of water quantity and quality;

- Increase recognition of the fisheries sector as an important sector for water management and planning among other stakeholders;

- Consideration of cooperation opportunities with international organizations and countries;

Exchange of experience and transfer of knowledge to support sustainable growth of fish production in the Kyrgyz Republic;

- Rational use of all types of reservoirs for fish production;

Developments in terms of ensuring product quality and safety are of undoubted importance. Conducting research aimed at improving the nutritional, taste and quality characteristics of aquaculture products, ensuring their food safety;

- Real development of fish farming is impossible without various long-term subsidies or other types of government support, especially at the initial stage of organizing production;

- Providing the fish production market with high-quality and safe feed.

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